

STRUCTURAL ELECTRONIC COMPONENTS BASED ON POLYMER NANOCOMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

High performance analog circuits that are embedded into structural parts are required for emerging applications such as sensing and structural health monitoring. Conductive inks recently developed towards in-situ sensing have shown promising results, yet offer only a superficial integration. Here, we propose a versatile fabrication of electrical components based on structural nanocomposites. Resistors, inductors, and capacitors are comprised of epoxy polymer and aligned carbon nanotubes (CNTs) and are fully integrated into a high frequency circuit. The structural electronics elements are not isotropic and have a modulus of $\sim 9.45 \pm 0.95$ GPa along the CNT axis (axial) and a transverse modulus of $\sim 6.86 \pm 0.69$ GPa. The elements are tested for piezoresistive response and are found to have a very low response ($<0.5\%$, giving a gage factor of 25) in the structural regime up to $2000\mu\epsilon$. Ranges of performance are 1-10 MOhm for resistance, 0.05-4 pF for capacitance, and 1-20 nH for inductance. An RLC circuit is fabricated from the above elements and characterized up to 10 GHz.

1 INTRODUCTION

With the emergence of new types of carbon allotropes with advantaged mass-specific properties, engineers have explored their integration into logic and analog systems for next generation electronic devices and integrated circuit systems [1]. In attempt to further reduce the node size currently limited by the lithographic resolution, engineers have investigated the tentative replacement of traditional silicon-based transistors with nanomaterials, such as single wall carbon nanotubes (SWCNT) and graphene. While many previous works report the successful fabrication of CNT based transistors (CNFET), large scale fabrication is limited by the need for specific tube chirality and a low yield [2]. Recently, Shulaker et al. developed a technique to use off-the-shelf SWCNT to build CNFET without sorting CNTs to build the first CNT computer [3]. Ideally, CNT-based logic and analog systems would be fully integrated into a singular three-dimensional (3D) chip sensor, where IC, analog circuit components, and antennas would be fabricated with the same materials.

Electronic circuits can already be printed using conductive ink. This technique shows excellent performance towards flexible devices [4]. Wearable electronics [5] and tattoos [6] have been demonstrated, where the electronic components were printed on the surface of a flexible substrate. 3D additive manufacturing techniques have been utilized to make 3D electrical components, such as resistors, capacitors, and inductors, as well as circuits and passive wireless sensors [7] that were fabricated using liquid metal as conductive traces. We propose here the facile fabrication and characterization of structural electronics components for high frequency ranges. Owing to their outstanding electrical properties and the versatility in integrating them at the macro scale, the possibility to leverage embedded analog systems within structural parts seems realizable. Polymer nanocomposites (PNCs) consisting of fillers dispersed in a resin matrix were discussed extensively in

the past decades. In particular, the high aspect ratio of CNTs and their inherent anisotropy, i.e., radial modulus $\sim 0.1 \times$ Young's modulus, provides the PNC with both improved mechanical and electrical performance [8,9], where CNT entanglements affect the performance of the composite. For instance, Lee et al. reported a low resistance in horizontally aligned long multiwalled CNT (MWCNTs) characterized with high electron conductivity along CNT-CNT junction paths. Similarly, the resistance perpendicular to the alignment axis, where entanglement is poor, was $\sim 10\times$ lower than the axial direction. Hence, dense and oriented CNT composites is a key factor in the performance of conductive elements.

In this report, we propose a facile process using multiwalled aligned CNT (A-CNT) arrays embedded into a structural polymer to form a PNC, thereby creating electrical components with added strength and multifunctionality. Based on the work of Lee et al. [8], which demonstrated that a wide range of resistance (R) is achieved by tailoring the morphology of a vertical array of MWCNTs, we demonstrate here the facile tailoring of CNT nanocomposite architectures to target a range of resistance $20 \Omega < R < 200 \Omega$, capacitance (C) $0.1 \text{ pF} < C < 4 \text{ pF}$, and inductance (L) $1 \text{ nH} < L < 60 \text{ nH}$. L-C serial circuit is prototyped as a proof of concept using the described structural electronic components.

2 METHODS

A-CNTs were grown via a procedure used in previous work [10]. Briefly, multiwalled CNTs were grown by thermal catalytic chemical vapor deposition (CVD) on silicon wafers using a thin catalyst layer of Fe/Al₂O₃ deposited by electron beam evaporation. Typically, CNT arrays have 1% volume fraction (V_f) of CNTs with the average CNT diameter of 8 nm in a CNT forest (99% air). The CNT length (l) depends on the growth time and ranges from 50 to 500 μm in this work. To fabricate the PNC, the CNT arrays were knocked down on a Teflon film as shown in Figure 1a. EPON 862 with the curing agent Epikure W® (Hexion) were mixed in a ratio of 100:26.4 and degassed for 20 min at 50°C to remove entrapped bubbles. Finally, the solution was spin-coated (9000 rpm rate) on the knocked-down A-CNTs (k-CNTs) film (see Fig. 1b) and cured in a vacuum oven for 4 hours at 149°C. The same process was used to fabricate inductors and capacitors, where interdigitated capacitors and planar inductors were pre-patterned on a silicon wafer using photolithography. After local deposition of the catalyst, the CNTs were grown following the same procedure as described for the resistor and then knocked down along a preferred CNT axis. Long CNTs ($300 < l < 500 \mu\text{m}$) were used in order to reduce any parasitic resistance, and mechanical and electrical performances of the structural electronics components were investigated up to frequencies of $f = 500 \text{ MHz}$. A coax fed patch antenna was fabricated using A-CNTs on a dielectric EPON 862 substrate. Briefly, a 60x60 mm² sheet of copper was attached to the bottom of a silicon mold of dimensions 60x60x3mm to form the ground layer. Subsequently, EPON 862 was mixed with Epikure as described above and was dropcast on top of the Cu layer in the silicon mold and cured in vacuum at 149°C for 4 hours. After curing, a small hole was drilled in the Cu/substrate at 5mm offset from the center to feed the antenna. After the cure was complete, an additional layer of EPON 862 was spin coated on the EPON substrate (at 4000 rpm) to allow the knock-down CNT patch to adhere to the substrate.

Figure 1. (a) Illustration of a structural resistor, capacitor, and inductor. (b) Basic fabrication process and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of A-CNT-based structural electronics utilizing epoxy.

The morphology of the PNCs was inspected using a scanning electron microscope (ZEISS, FESEM ultraplus) operated at 5kv. structural performances of the PNC were tested for $l=500 \mu\text{m}$ PNC in dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA). DMA testing provides information on the thermo-mechanical properties of the PNC. Piezoresistivity at a strain up to $2000 \mu\epsilon$ was tested in a tensile configuration along and perpendicular to the CNT axis. resistance in dc was tested on a 4 probe station, and the impedance of resistors, capacitors, and inductors was tested on an impedance analyzer (Agilent 4395a) at frequencies ranging from $f = 10\text{-}500 \text{ MHz}$. the circuit was tested on a vector network analyzer (HP8510c) at $f = 0.2\text{-}10 \text{ GHz}$.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Resistors

Figure 1a shows an illustration of the PNC electronics fabrication process, where aligned CNTs are knocked down to provide a conductive path. Depending on the CNT length used in the PNC resistor ($1 \text{ cm} \times 1 \text{ cm}$ square), varying resistances are obtained ranging from $R \sim 20 \Omega$ for $l = 500 \mu\text{m}$ to $R \sim 200 \Omega$ for $l = 20 \mu\text{m}$, as seen in Figure 2a. Moreover, the resistance along the alignment axis is generally lower than the resistance perpendicular to the alignment in short CNTs, where entanglement is rare, and the junction density is poor. Figure 2b shows the absolute impedance and Z/R factor for 2 selected resistors: $l = 500 \mu\text{m}$ and $l = 50 \mu\text{m}$. The testing reveals that both resistors are extremely stable and exhibit no apparent noise when measured at high frequency ($f = 500 \text{ MHz}$), making those resistors very attractive for high frequency electronics [11]. We should note that the impedance testing also reveals a strong anisotropy of the resistors (not shown here) with higher impedance in the transverse direction. This same anisotropy is also observed in the mechanical performance of the resistors.

Figure 2. Structural resistor. (a) resistance and anisotropy factor vs. CNT length and orientation. (b) Axial and transverse impedance performance for $l = 50 \mu\text{m}$ and $l = 500 \mu\text{m}$ resistor.

Dynamic Mechanical Analysis was performed on the resistors in a tensile configuration, when they were loaded along and perpendicular to the CNT axis. Mechanical properties tested for the $l = 500 \mu\text{m}$ PNC resistor in a tensile configuration revealed a Young's modulus $E_{\parallel} \sim 3 \text{ GPa}$ and $E_{\perp} \sim 1.5 \text{ GPa}$ along and perpendicular to the CNT axis, respectively (see Figure 3). As expected, lower modulus is observed for shorter CNTs ($l = 50 \mu\text{m}$). Beyond mechanical properties, we should note that the relaxation transitions in the polymer (Epon) are strongly influenced by the length of the CNT, with the appearance of several secondary transitions noted at 150°C when long CNTs are present. This point has not yet been elucidated.

Figure 3. DMTA of resistor loaded perpendicular (transverse, left) and along (axial, right) to the CNT axis.

For structural materials, we expect the electronic properties to be independent of strain. Therefore, the piezoresistive response of the structural resistor ($l = 500 \mu\text{m}$) was investigated under tensile axial and transverse loading. Figure 4 demonstrates a very low strain effect on the resistance with a calculated constant gauge factor of $GF_{\parallel} \sim 1$ and $GF_{\perp} \sim 0.25$ in the axial and transverse directions, respectively.

Figure 4. Piezoresistivity and gauge factor for PNCs with $l = 500 \mu\text{m}$ in both axial and transverse orientations. Part (a) represents 2 test samples for reproducibility.

3.2 Inductors and Capacitors

Next, we used $l = 500 \mu\text{m}$ resistors as conductive traces to fabricate capacitors and inductors, as shown in Figure 1a. The $l = 500 \mu\text{m}$ devices have the lowest resistance and piezoresistive response, making them ideal for conductive traces. Capacitors were fabricated as interdigitated electrodes with pre-designed length and inter-electrodes distance. Epon here acts as the dielectric polymer. We show that varying the number of electrodes slightly changes the capacitance (C) measured up to $f = 500 \text{ M Hz}$. One should note that the capacitance stays relatively stable over the frequency range with a parasitic $R \sim 100 \Omega$ (see Figure 5). Capacitances in the range of $C = 0.1 \text{ pF} - 5 \text{ pF}$ were achieved by varying the number (N) and the distance (s) between the electrodes (see Table 1). The same process was used to fabricate the structural inductors (see Figure 6). We demonstrate that varying the size of the outer diameter (L_0) of the inductors allows a range of inductances $L = 10\text{-}20 \text{ nH}$ (see Table 2). As observed for the structural resistors, our structural capacitors and inductors reveal ideal behavior at high frequency, making them very attractive for RF circuits.

Figure 5. Structural capacitor (a) impedance and (b) reactance for $s = 0.5 \text{ mm}$ capacitor and for increasing number of electrodes.

Table 1. Dimension and performance of structural capacitors.

L (μm)	w (μm)	N	s (μm)	Measured C (pF)
500	4500	16	500	2.2
500	4500	10	500	0.7
500	4500	9	500	0.4
500	4500	10	300	4.1
500	4500	6	300	1.9
500	4500	2	300	0.1
500	4500	9	200	4.1
500	4500	6	200	3.9
500	4500	5	200	3.9

Figure 6. Structural inductor (a) impedance and (b) reactance for $N=0.75$ turn and for increasing inner diameter L_0 .

Table 2. Dimensions and performance of structural capacitors.

N	L_0 [mm]	L [nH]
2.5	10	85
2.5	5	61
1.7	4	12
1.5	3	6.7
1	4	4
0.75	6	11
0.75	9	13
0.75	12	19

3.3 RLC circuit

Finally, predesigned capacitors and inductors were integrated into a circuit and tested on a vector network analyzer at $f < 10$ GHz. A photograph of the circuit is shown in Figure 7a along with the equivalent RF circuit block. The capacitor and inductor with $C = 1$ pF and $L = 15$ nH respectively, were connected in series with PNC ($l = 500$ μm) traces (see Figure 3a). The S-parameters collected were translated into Z values and showed excellent agreement with RF serial L-C circuit equivalent models (see red graph in Figure 7b) that estimated the RLC series circuit parameters $R_c = 2.5$ Ω , $L_c = 1.63$ nH, and $C = 1.96$ pF for the capacitor, and $R_L = 4$ Ω , $L = 0.88$ nH, and $C_L = 2.15$ pF for the inductor at $f = 3.5$ GHz.

Figure 7. L-C circuit fabricated with structural electronics. (a) Optical image of the circuit and equivalent RF serial L-C circuit. (b) Impedance (blue) and fit for equivalent circuit models (red).

4. CONCLUSIONS

We report the facile fabrication and testing of structural electronics, where patterning of the CNT catalyst is employed to design the shape of the structural electronic elements. The conductive path is realized by knocking down vertically aligned CNTs while preserving a preferred orientation and simultaneously densifying the CNT network. Upon densification, a highly conductive path is formed with resistance depending on the CNT length and orientation. Finally, a structural polymer is added to form a polymer nanocomposite with superior modulus and tunable resistance. Following the same procedure, we report the fabrication of inductors and capacitors and their integration in an LC circuit. Capacitors in the range of 0.1-5 pF and inductors in the range of 4-100nH were fabricated. Performance up to 500 MHz shows minimum noise and impedance loss, revealing the advantage of using structural components at high frequencies (up to 500 MHz). When tested beyond that frequency, noise must be considered in the circuit analysis.

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